

APPLICATION OF SATELLITE REMOTE SENSING METHODS FOR THE MAPPING OF HARD-TO-ACCESS AREAS

Nataliya Aleksandrova¹, Asparuh Kamburov¹, Lyubomir Ivanov²

¹University of Mining and Geology “St. Ivan Rilski”, 1700 Sofia; E-mail: nataliya.aleksandrova@mgu.bg

²Institute of Mathematics and Informatics, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1113 Sofia; E-mail: lyubomail@yahoo.com

Corresponding author: nataliya.aleksandrova@mgu.bg

ABSTRACT. The article presents an innovative methodology for using satellite remote sensing methods as a fast and affordable way to produce cartographic products. Three main data sources are analysed: 1) the *Sentinel* satellite mission - multispectral data from the *Sentinel 2B* satellite were used; 2) the *Landsat* satellite mission - data from the *Landsat 8* satellite were used; 3) Reference Elevation Model of Antarctica (REMA), built from a set of multiple individual stereoscopic digital elevation models extracted from satellite images from the *WorldView-1*, *WorldView-2*, *WorldView-3*, and *GeoEye-1* missions. As a result of data processing from *Sentinel 2B* and *Landsat 8*, classified raster datasets were obtained, and a model with terrain contours from the Reference Elevation Model. The experimental part includes the creation of a topographic map at a scale of 1:50 000 for a selected geographical area (the Havre Mountains on Alexander Island, Antarctica), with a spatial resolution corresponding to terrain element size of 2 m. The toponymical data for the geographical features on the map were provided by the Antarctic Place-Names Commission at the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Bulgaria.

Key words: remote sensing, cartography, REMA, Sentinel, Landsat.

ПРИЛОЖЕНИЕ НА СПЪТНИКОВИ ДИСТАНЦИОННИ МЕТОДИ ЗА КАРТОГРАФИРАНЕ НА ТРУДНОДОСТЪПНИ ОБЛАСТИ

Наталия Александрова¹, Аспарух Камбуров¹, Любомир Иванов²

¹Минно-геоложки университет „Св. Иван Рилски“, 1700 София

²Институт по математика и информатика, Българска академия на науките, 1113 София

РЕЗЮМЕ. Статията представя една иновативна методология за използване на спътникови методи за дистанционни изследвания като бърз и достъпен начин за производство на картографски продукти. Анализирани са три основни източника на данни: 1) спътникова мисия Sentinel – използвани са мултиспектрални данни от спътникова мисия Sentinel-2; 2) спътникова мисия Landsat - използвани са мултиспектрални данни от спътникова мисия Landsat 8; 3) референтен височинен модел на Антарктида (REMA), формиран от набор на множество индивидуални стереоскопични цифрови модели на релефа, генерирани от спътникови изображения, получени от мисиите WorldView-1, WorldView-2, WorldView-3 и GeoEye-1. В резултат на обработката на данните от Sentinel-2 и Landsat-8 са получени класифицирани резултати за теренното покритие, а от референтния височинен модел – модел с хоризонтални на терена. Експерименталната част включва създаване на топографска карта в мащаб 1:50 000 за избран географски район (планината Хавър на остров Александър, Антарктида), с пространствена разделителна способност, която съответства на размер на теренния елемент от 2 м. Топонимните данни за географските обекти в картата са предоставени от Комисията по антарктически наименования към Министерство на външните работи на България.

Ключови думи: дистанционни методи, картография, REMA, Sentinel, Landsat.

Introduction

The main objective of the study is the integration of open access geospatial data (satellite data and digital terrain model) and the application of remote sensing methods as a fast and affordable way to produce map products for hard-to-access areas of the Earth's surface. To test the methodology, a 1:50 000 scale topographic map of a selected geographic area (Alexander Island, Antarctica) was created. The topographic map represents in graphical form the relief of the Havre Mountains, including peaks, saddles, glaciers, coastline and rocky areas free of snow and ice. The selected area is of historical significance as it was one of the original options for the construction of a polar station in 1988 as part of the First Bulgarian Antarctic Expedition.

The presented methods for processing satellite remote sensing data allow the provision of reliable information about the objects located on the Earth's surface, which is of particular importance for hard-to-reach areas. Similar research which, however, uses the synthetic aperture radar (SAR) methods, has been published for the glaciers of Livingston Island by Atanasova (2023) and Atanasova & Nikolov (2022).

Data sources for the methodology

The methodology used data from the Reference Elevation Model of Antarctica (REMA) for the Alexander Island region, combined with additional multispectral satellite optical imagery, which was processed in a GIS environment.

The application of methods for processing the multispectral satellite images data are used for computer-aided (automatic) classification of non-snow-covered rocks and snow cover by using the Normalised Difference Snow Index (NDSI) (Dozier, 1989), while the Normalised Difference Water Index (NDWI) was applied to distinguish water areas from snow cover (McFeeters, 1996).

Satellites, such as *Landsat 8* and *Sentinel-2*, which provide data in the visible and infrared regions of the electromagnetic spectrum, are suitable for distinguishing different types of land cover; for the continent of Antarctica, these are objects such as snow, rocks, water areas.

The *Landsat 8* satellite has nine spectral bands from the Operational Land Imager (OLI) sensor and two spectral bands from the Thermal Infrared Sensor (TIRS), which have different spatial resolutions: from 15 m, 30 m, 60 m for OLI images and up to 100 m for TIRS images. By processing *Landsat 8* OLI-TIRS images, maps that provide tracking data for the dynamics of the spatial distribution of snow cover were created (Stoyanov, 2024).

The *Sentinel-2* satellite has thirteen spectral bands, with four bands in the visible spectral region and nine bands in the near-infrared to shortwave infrared regions; the bands have different spatial resolutions ranging from 10 m to 60 m.

Landsat and *Sentinel-2* satellite imageries are freely available from several platforms, such as Copernicus Open Access Hub, USGS EROS Archive, Google Earth Engine.

Geospatial data on snow-covered areas, cliffs, coastal margin, etc., for the Antarctic region are available on the Antarctic Digital Database website (ADD) (<http://www.add.scar.org>)

It is possible to combine data from both passive and active sensor systems for snow cover mapping (Wang et al., 2018). This is a good approach when there are difficulties to distinguish clouds from snow, as optical sensors cannot work effectively in high cloud cover areas with snow cover (Grenfell et al., 1994). Synthetic aperture radar systems provide information on surface texture and structure to distinguish between snowy and rocky terrain.

Software products used for processing, analysis, and visualisation of geospatial data obtained by remote sensing methods are commercial products, such as ERDAS Imagine, ArcGIS, ENVI, Global Mapper, as well as open-source software such as QGIS, GRASS GIS, SNAP, SAGA GIS.

Interpretation and processing of satellite data and REMA model data

Suitable multispectral data from the *Landsat 8* OLI/TIRS satellite missions (Fig. 1) and *Sentinel-2 L1C* were selected to perform the precision mapping. The cloud-free satellite images used in the processing were selected because the main difficulty is not to detect snow when the atmosphere is cloud-free, but to prevent errors in its identification among clouds. The choice of satellite data from the summer period for the Alexander Island area was made, taking into account some specificities of the region:

- rocky areas are supposed to be more visible in the summer season, although even when temperatures are higher, snow and ice are still significant;
- cloud-covered areas are also supposed to be significantly less, compared to the winter period, although this depends on the specific weather conditions.

Fig. 1. Landsat 8 scene (Earth Resources Observatory and Science (EROS) Center (2020). *Landsat 8-9 Operational Land Imager / Thermal Infrared Sensor Level-2, Collection 2* [dataset]. U.S. Geological Survey. <https://doi.org/10.5066/P9OGBGM6>)

The digital elevation model that was applied to generate the terrain contours was derived from the Reference Elevation Model of Antarctica.

Satellite data

Sentinel-2 L1C satellite image data were used to distinguish snow- and ice-free areas of the Alexander Island terrain cover, and the result is presented in false colours composite - a selection that provides the best visual distinctiveness.

A suitable spectral combination of bands to distinguish snow, ice, and snow- and ice-free areas of the terrain cover is: Blue, SWIR1, and SWIR2, as these bands are highly reflective in the visible part of the electromagnetic spectrum and highly absorptive in the shortwave infrared. The assignment of the spectral bands to the corresponding colours for visualisation was done in order to obtain the best visual discrimination for the analysed object classes. Since the only band used in the visible region is Blue and in these synthetic images it is by the colour red, snow and ice appear bright red. The more ice there is, the stronger the absorption in the shortwave infrared bands and the lower the intensity in these bands, resulting in a more intense red colour (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Part of a Sentinel-2 Sensor Level-1C scene, with an appropriate spectral band combination applied to distinguish terrain cover containing snow, ice, and snow- and ice-free terrain areas

Thick ice and snow appear bright red, while small ice crystals in high altitude clouds appear red-orange to very pale orange. In the presence of vegetation, it will appear greenish in this combination of spectral bands. Sections of ground cover that are free of snow and ice are visible in bright blue colour in the image.

Although the Normalised Difference Snow Index is useful for evaluation, i.e., it is the best index for snow mapping, the processing was performed by applying machine learning methods from an interpreter (supervised classification method), since using an index does not provide satisfactory results in distinguishing snow cover from clouds. Object-based classification was applied and six training samples (training polygons) were formed for: water, rock, shadow, shaded rock, snow, and snow in water. Based on the training polygons, class descriptions are generated, obtained in a supervised classification mode (Marinov, et al. 2016). After classification, a vector description of these object classes was formed. The vectors describing non-snow-covered rock areas were used to

produce the map. Identification and mapping of land cover changes, based on computer-aided visual interpretation of satellite imagery, was carried out as part of the pan-European CORINE Land Cover project (Koleva, et al. 2018). The sampling by major strata and substrates for the CLC012 and CLCCH2006-12 products included bare rocks and perpetual snow.

The results obtained on the data using the REMA elevation model are compared with data obtained on two indices: the Normalised Difference Snow Index $\{NDSI=(VIS-SWIR)/(VIS+SWIR)\}$ and the Normalised Difference Water Index $\{NDWI=(GREEN-NIR)/(GREEN+NIR)\}$ applied on a *Landsat 8* image. The Normalised Difference Snow Index data represent a spectral band ratio that is determined from the spectral differences of snow in the shortwave infrared and visible spectral bands to identify snow relative to other features in a scene. In the visible wavelengths of the electromagnetic spectrum, snow cover is as bright as clouds and is therefore difficult to distinguish from areas obscured by clouds. In the band with 1.6-micron wavelength, the snow cover absorbs sunlight and, therefore, appears much darker than clouds. This makes it possible to distinguish snow cover from clouds. NDSI values > 0.4 usually indicate the presence of snow.

Reference Elevation Model of Antarctica

The Reference Elevation Model of Antarctica is a digital elevation model with a spatial terrain resolution of 2 m, developed and maintained since 2017 by the Polar Geospatial Center (PGC), a research centre at the University of Minnesota, USA. The model is built by stereophotogrammetric processing of satellite imagery over a 12-year period, and its latest version (2) is dated October 2022. REMA is generated by applying fully automated techniques - stereo autocorrelation of overlapping pairs of optical satellite images, with high spatial resolution from *WorldView-1*, *WorldView-2*, *WorldView-3* and *GeoEye-1* acquired between 2009 and 2021, using open-source Surface Extraction from TIN-based *Searchspace Minimisation (SETSM)* software developed at the Ohio University. Each DEM was vertically referenced with satellite altimetry measurements from *Cryosat-2* and *ICESat*. REMA data are available under a *Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Public License (CC-BY-4.0)* (Howat et al., 2022).

The processing of the REMA elevation model data and satellite data, as well as the production of the topographic map, are performed in ArcGIS Pro software environment, version 3.4. The raw REMA data are available as overlapping strips of different shapes and sizes, and as a product in the form of 50x50 km square raster mosaics georeferenced in the WGS-84 geodetic reference system (geographic coordinates and ellipsoid heights). Mosaics with identifiers 38_09_1_1_2m_v2.0 and 38_09_1_2_2m_v2.0 are used for the map.

Case study: topographic map of the Havre Mountains on Alexander Island, Antarctica

History and toponymy

The Havre Mountains are a large mountain group forming the northwestern region of Alexander Island, Antarctica. They were first seen in 1821 by a Russian expedition under the command of Fabian Gottlieb von Bellingshausen. They were originally mapped with approximate accuracy by the French Antarctic Expedition, 1908-10, under Jean-Baptiste Charcot, who named them after Le Havre, the French port from which

their ship sailed. The mountains were mapped in more detail in the 1960s from aerial photographs taken by the Ronne Antarctic Research Expedition, 1947-48 (SCAR 2025b). The toponymy of the Havre Mountains evolved, as more land and air surveys were carried out in the area and new mapping became available. Most of the later mapping of the Havre Mountains was also British.

The Havre Mountains were surveyed by the British geologists Bernard Care and Richard Burn in 1976/77, and by a British-Bulgarian team comprising geologists Hristo Pimpirev, Borislav Kamenov (both part of the first Bulgarian Antarctic Expedition) and Philip Nell, and mountain guide and medic Peter Marquis in 1987/88. Apart from their geological field work, operating from the team's base camp in the foothills of St. George Peak (1008 m a.s.l.), Pimpirev and Kamenov chose some appropriate location for a possible Bulgarian base near Balgari Nunatak at Cape Vostok at the northwest extremity of the Havre Mountains. Four other members of the Bulgarian expedition sailed on board the Soviet *Mihail Somov* scientific expedition ship commanded by Captain Feliks Pesyakov, and the two groups were to get together and assemble a couple of huts on the chosen location on Alexander Island. However, that plan failed and the huts were installed on Livingston Island instead (Pimpirev 2013, Ivanov & Ivanova 2022).

There are 72 marked geographic features on the 2025 Bulgarian map, comprising 42 named features and 30 nameless elevations. The names have been given by Bulgaria (21), the United Kingdom (12), the USA (5), Russia (2), and France (2). These could be divided into several categories: Musicians 8; Bulgarian geography 7; Antarctic history 6; British research and support personnel 5; US research and support personnel 5; Bulgarian history 3; French research and support personnel 2; French geography 1; Russian royalty 1; Russian culture 1; Bulgarian culture 1; History of science 1; Descriptive 1.

The local toponymy expanded over time with the following: 2 Russian names in 1821, 2 French in 1912, 6 British in 1961, 1 American in 1969, 5 British and 4 American in 1980, 1 Bulgarian in 1989, 1 British in 2015, and 20 Bulgarian ones in 2017 (SCAR 2025b).

Topographic map of the Havre Mountains

The map is created in the following sequence:

1. Selection of map coordinate system – WGS-84 UTM projection, zone 19S, height system - geoid model EGM96.
2. Coordinate and height transformations of input digital raster data from REMA.
3. Input of vector point layer with toponym data.
4. Creation of 20 m sectional height contours, with index contours multiple of 100.
5. Coastline delineation - for this purpose a contour with a value of 5 m was generated and selected as the coastline boundary. Verification of the coast boundaries was performed by comparison with the Antarctic Digital Database data (ADD_coastline_high_res_line_v7_9 layer), with which the 5 m contour matches to a good approximation for the mapped area (Fig. 3). The coastline is also matched with data derived from two indices, the Normalised Difference Snow Index and the Normalised Difference Water Index.

Fig. 3. Part of the map with a discrepancy between the shoreline from ADD data (black contour) and the 5 m contour from REMA (dark blue contour)

6. Smoothing of contour under topological conditions of non-intersection with other geographic objects (peaks, coastline, etc.) using the Polynomial Approximation with Exponential Kernel (PAEK) method with a 500 m tolerance and removal of contours with circumference less than 200 m, reported as noise in the REMA DEM.

7. Input and representation of a vector polygon layer with boundaries of ice and snow-free areas (generated from Landsat and Sentinel satellite data).

8. Geographical feature labels – set of labels for the following feature classes: glaciers, bays, peaks, saddles, nameless characteristic heights (respectively those covered or not covered with ice/snow), camp of the British-Bulgarian geological survey of 1987/88. The proper visualisation of the location of features, such as glaciers and saddles, the orientation of the inscriptions, and their colouring were done on a height-coloured pad from the REMA digital model (Fig. 4)

Fig. 4. Part of the topographic map for the Alexander Island area - labels of glaciers and peaks in the Havre Mountains area

9. Creation of the final cartographic product - scaling, metadata input, out-of-frame layout (Fig. 5). The map is published with ISBN 978-619-90008-0-9 (soft cover) and ISBN 978-619-92883-0-6 (digital format PNG).

Conclusion

As a result of the case studies, the following main results can be summarised:

- A methodology for creating digital topographic models and maps of different geographic areas using satellite data and elevation models with appropriate spatial resolution was developed;

- The cartographic products which can be created using this methodology are applicable to a wide range of users in science and practice, including in mining for modelling processes in open pits and open-cast mines;
- The methodology allows the use of remote sensing data as a quick and easy way to produce mapping products for hard-to-reach areas;
- When mapping snowy areas, it is necessary to select appropriate combinations of spectral bands in order to best distinguish the classes of objects analysed: rocks not covered by snow and ice from snowy areas.

Fig. 5. A map version with ice-free areas from satellite data processing (vector polygons in yellow and pink)

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